

User policy for NorCP data

23 September 2024, v1

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13827561](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13827561)

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Important to read before using the data

The user shall have a dialogue with one of the contact points (listed below) before using the data. The purpose is to build potential collaborations and get feedback about the data, as well as to avoid misunderstandings about the data and model setup.

If planning to use NorCP data in publications we encourage authors to offer co-authorship to members of the NorCP group.

Acknowledgment and Citation

Please cite the following publications whenever NorCP datasets are used in a scientific publication,

- For studies including the model evaluation runs (1998-2018):

Lind, P., Belušić, D., Christensen, O. B., Dobler, A., Kjellström, E., Landgren, O., Lindstedt, D., Matte, D., Pedersen, R. A., Toivonen, E., & Wang, F. (2020). Benefits and added value of convection-permitting climate modeling over Fenno-Scandinavia. *Climate Dynamics*, 55(7), 1893–1912. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-020-05359-3>

- For studies including climate projections:

Lind, P., Belušić, D., Médus, E., Dobler, A., Pedersen, R. A., Wang, F., Matte, D., Kjellström, E., Landgren, O., Lindstedt, D., Christensen, O. B., & Christensen, J. H., (2022) Climate change information over Fenno-Scandinavia produced with a convection-permitting climate model, *Climate Dynamics* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-022-06589-3>

Also add the following sentences in the Acknowledgement:

This work uses data from the NorCP project, which is a Nordic collaboration involving climate modeling groups from the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), Finnish

Meteorological Institute (FMI), Norwegian Meteorological Institute (MET Norway) and the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI).

Scientific use

Findings resulting from non-commercial research shall be shared openly through public publications and shall not be considered proprietary.

Commercial use

Special conditions apply when using the NorCP datasets for commercial purposes before their publication on ESGF:

(1) **Notification to NorCP Members:** Prior to sharing the data for commercial purpose, inform NorCP members about the intended use to prevent any conflicts with ongoing studies and potential climate services;

(2) **Legal Agreement for Data Liability:** A legal agreement shall be established that excludes the data provider from responsibility for potential data errors.

For both Scientific use and Commercial use

(1) All users must ensure that they do not distribute the data to any third parties.

(2) In order to improve understanding of model performance and to foster model improvements, users must cooperate with NorCP data providers by responding to reasonable requests for feedback on research outcomes. This feedback may include reporting model deficiencies or documenting NorCP publications, among other tasks.

(3) Potential limitations exist in the data, which may include, though not exclusively, errors within the models, deficiencies in experimental designs, and other unforeseen errors/limitations. It's important to note that no specific individual, organization, or group is responsible for these limitations.

(4) A Digital Object Identifier (DOI) may be assigned to NorCP data as part of the data publication process. Users are kindly requested to make use of the DOI, where it is available and applicable, for citing the data in their publications.

Feedback and contact information

Any feedback or questions about the datasets is highly appreciated and can be sent to norcp@met.no.